

Supplementary Material: Decentralized Low-Latency Task Scheduling for Ad-Hoc Computing

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I. INTRODUCTION

This document provides supplementary material for interested readers of [1]. It contains an overview of the evaluation results, the parameter study of Drift and Bandit scheduling in more detail, and the results of the additional experiment covering task queuing. Please note: Parts of the paper’s text are reused here to provide a self-contained explanation of the tables and figures in this document.

II. TASK AND JOB COMPLETION TIMES

Table I compares the task and job completion times of the central scheduling algorithms and the three basic decentralized scheduling algorithms. Table II contains the same metrics for the best central scheduling approach, the two novel decentralized approaches, and the omniscient scheduler.

TABLE I

TASK AND JOB METRICS FOR BASIC CENTRALIZED AND DECENTRALIZED SCHEDULING ALGORITHMS

(HIGHLIGHTED: LOWEST TASK COMPLETION TIMES, LOWEST JOB COMPLETION TIMES, AND FEWEST DEADLINE MISSES PER LOAD)

Load	Algorithm	Tasks		Jobs		
		Total	Exec.	Mean	Median	% Misses
Lowest	C-RND	0.794	0.265	1.111	0.976	46.39
	C-GRD	0.588	0.060	0.639	0.632	0.01
	D-RND	0.550	0.257	0.910	0.786	29.39
	D-PRP	0.413	0.139	0.756	0.646	17.24
	D-GRD	0.524	0.055	0.893	0.866	34.39
Low	C-RND	0.789	0.261	1.109	0.976	46.51
	C-GRD	0.592	0.064	0.646	0.638	0.06
	D-RND	0.553	0.251	0.932	0.818	32.14
	D-PRP	0.414	0.140	0.757	0.647	17.58
	D-GRD	0.576	0.055	1.035	0.990	49.18
Medium	C-RND	0.795	0.249	1.134	0.974	46.15
	C-GRD	0.615	0.073	0.690	0.649	1.30
	D-RND	0.552	0.237	0.958	0.855	34.56
	D-PRP	0.412	0.137	0.752	0.644	16.96
	D-GRD	0.635	0.055	1.216	1.161	65.18
High	C-RND	1.928	0.242	3.612	1.006	50.71
	C-GRD	1.744	0.093	3.139	0.669	9.78
	D-RND	0.558	0.229	0.995	0.896	38.47
	D-PRP	0.413	0.138	0.755	0.647	17.17
	D-GRD	0.678	0.056	1.391	1.315	74.96
Highest	C-RND	20.116	0.230	40.504	1.158	62.40
	C-GRD	19.921	0.133	39.986	0.735	30.74
	D-RND	0.568	0.216	1.049	0.954	44.66
	D-PRP	0.414	0.138	0.763	0.655	17.42
	D-GRD	0.715	0.056	1.585	1.476	81.45

TABLE II

TASK AND JOB METRICS FOR BEST CENTRALIZED AND DECENTRALIZED SCHEDULING ALGORITHMS IN COMPARISON TO THE OMNISCIENT DECENTRALIZED SCHEDULER

Load	Algorithm	Tasks		Jobs		
		Total	Exec.	Mean	Median	% Misses
Lowest	D-OMNI	0.330	0.056	0.379	0.369	0.00
	C-GRD	0.588	0.060	0.639	0.632	0.01
	DFT	0.348	0.059	0.442	0.401	0.21
	BND	0.346	0.072	0.419	0.398	0.01
Low	D-OMNI	0.332	0.058	0.381	0.372	0.00
	C-GRD	0.592	0.064	0.646	0.638	0.06
	DFT	0.352	0.061	0.451	0.408	0.30
	BND	0.346	0.073	0.419	0.399	0.01
Medium	D-OMNI	0.333	0.059	0.385	0.374	0.00
	C-GRD	0.615	0.073	0.690	0.649	1.30
	DFT	0.354	0.063	0.462	0.415	0.51
	BND	0.345	0.071	0.418	0.397	0.01
High	D-OMNI	0.336	0.062	0.392	0.379	0.01
	C-GRD	1.744	0.093	3.139	0.669	9.78
	DFT	0.360	0.068	0.476	0.426	0.77
	BND	0.346	0.072	0.421	0.400	0.01
Highest	D-OMNI	0.343	0.070	0.405	0.386	0.17
	C-GRD	19.921	0.133	39.986	0.735	30.74
	DFT	0.369	0.075	0.500	0.445	1.30
	BND	0.347	0.071	0.427	0.404	0.02

III. DRIFT AND BANDIT PARAMETER STUDY

We perform an extensive, preliminary parameter study for the *Drift* and *Bandit* algorithms to study the influence of the parameters and to select suitable configurations for the evaluation. We first analyze the *Drift* algorithm which is adjustable with the number of rejections that reduces the scheduling window size η_r , the number of rejections that increases the scheduling window size η_i , and the number of previous tasks in the scheduling history h . In this experiment, we set the history length to $h = 100$. We observed similar patterns for other history lengths in supplementary tests ($h = 10, 20, 50$). Figure 1 depicts job completion times for different η_r and η_i in the five load scenarios. Similar patterns are visible as far as deadline misses are concerned. In general, job completion times are reduced with cautious window reduction, i.e., only when the number of rejections is very low the target window is reduced. Further, we observe that the optimal η_i increases with the load. This happens because a small η_i quickly extends the window w which results in a larger task execution time.

Fig. 1: Analysis of decentralized *Drift* scheduling. We study the impact of η_i and η_r on the average job completion time. Recall that $\eta_i > \eta_r$. For a fixed scheduling history size of $h = 100$, the scheduling window size is reduced if the algorithm observes less rejections than η_r . More rejections than η_i result in an increasing window size. We observe that, in general, low values for η_r , i.e., cautious window reduction, i.e., reduction only when the number of rejections is very low, yields lower job completion times. Further, we observe a shift in η_i for increasing load towards larger values which is because a small η_i quickly extends the window w and slower providers are selected.

We now perform a parameter study for the *Bandit* provider selection algorithm. We vary two parameters: the bucket creation heuristic (*leapfrogged* vs. *performance-aware*) and the bucket size. Figure 2 provides an overview of the job completion times for both heuristics and different bucket sizes under different loads. We first observe that the bucket size has a smaller influence for leapfrogged buckets. In general, leapfrogged bucket creation increases the mean and variance of job completion times. This is due to the fact that all buckets also contain slow providers which are selected when a consumer sends out multiple tasks. Performance-aware bucket creation outperforms leapfrogged bucket creation in terms of job completion times. In the highest load scenario, performance-aware (480 ms, with bucket size 5) is 46% faster than leapfrogged bucket creation (768 ms, with bucket size 20). In contrast to leapfrogged bucket creation, performance-aware bucket creation is sensitive to the bucket size parameter. Across all load scenarios, there is a tendency that small buckets perform better than larger bucket sizes. In summary, we conclude that the optimal settings for the *Bandit* algorithm are the same throughout our study whereas the configuration of the *Drift* algorithm has to be adapted to the load.

IV. TASK QUEUEING EXPERIMENT

While we analyzed the results from the other simulations, we observed that even under the highest load, the fast providers were not working to full capacity. Once they have finished the execution of a task, they have to wait for the next one to arrive. Thus, we perform an additional experiment that introduces task queues at the resource providers. Task queues avoid idle times and allow the TVMs to seamlessly execute one task after another. As a downside, a long queue might increase the task completion time as it introduces queuing delays. We experiment with different queue sizes between 1 and 5 tasks for both the *Drift* and the *Bandit* algorithm. Figure 3 shows the results for the *Drift* algorithm. The results for the *Bandit* algorithm look similar. To better demonstrate the effect of queuing on the task completion time, we removed transfer and result handling times from the figure as they are similar across all settings. The results visualize the major trade-off in queuing. We observe that a larger queue size

Fig. 2: Analysis of bucket creation heuristic (Performance-aware vs. Leapfrogged) and bucket size of the *Bandit* algorithm in different load scenarios. Performance-aware bucket creation leads to faster job completion times than leapfrogged bucket creation if the bucket size is set to small values. The leapfrogged creation generates buckets with comparable execution speeds.

increases the queuing time because tasks need to wait until they are processed. However, the execution time decreases with the queue size because fast providers can be used more efficiently. These opposing effects result in decreasing task and job completion times for small queue sizes. Under high load, this effect reverses for larger queue sizes. The second effect of queuing is a substantial decrease in deadline misses. Whereas the *Drift* algorithm without queuing resulted in 4.51% of deadline misses under the highest load, increasing the queue size led to 1.38% misses for D-DFT-1 and 1.77% for D-DFT-5. For the *Bandit* algorithm these numbers range from 0.23% (D-BND-1) to 0.02% (D-BND-5). In summary, queuing does not only reduce the mean job completion time but further eliminates most deadline misses.

Fig. 3: Analysis of different maximum queue sizes and their impact on task completion times (stacked bars) and job completion times (blue markers) for *Drift* scheduling. We observe that queuing reduces job completion times, especially in high load scenarios. Increasing the maximum queue size leads to lower execution times at the cost of increasing queuing times. We observe similar effects for *Bandit* scheduling.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Edinger, M. Breitbach, N. Gabrisch, D. Schäfer, C. Becker, and A. Rizk, "Decentralized Low-Latency Task Scheduling for Ad-Hoc Computing," in *Proc. IPDPS*. IEEE, 2021, to be published.